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**A SURVEY OF EFFECT OF MINDFULNESS MEDITATION ON THE
STUDENTS OF G.S.B'S SMT. SURAJBA COLLEGE
OF EDUCATION.**

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‘We all need to wake up. We all need to live more. We all need to get out of our heads. We all need to stop worrying. We all need to push fear aside. We all need to stop everything for a while. We all need to breathe deeper’

Abstracts -:

The present age is the age of rapid change of competitions. Meditation is an art which connects our soul, mind, and body together. It makes us strong, flexible, peaceful and healthy personality. In country like India where people have so much stress and are fatigue, Meditation is very necessary. It makes us fit and healthy. A healthy mind can do everything. These days, people don't have time for meditation due to their daily tasks, work, and stressful life. Maintaining a good health is much important than growing financially because without health you cannot work and without working you cannot earn.

The study originally was intended to determine the affect of meditation on blood pressure and benefit of meditation for young people and Students with high blood pressure, stress, anxiety seems to become lower side. The results were emphatic and clearly demonstrated that meditation significantly reduced blood pressure in all situations.

This study was then expanded to measure the affects of meditation on other aspects of student life.

Here are the findings of this research.

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- **Improved Concentration:** Students were able to concentrate better and had more mental focus.
- **Reduced Blood Pressure:** This reduction in blood pressure was regardless of whether the students were facing a stressful situation, like an examination, or not.
- **Decreased Absenteeism & Tardiness:** In addition, meditation also reduced behavior problems.
- **Better Grades:** Students felt they were doing better with their homework and school work as well.
- **Improved Interpersonal Relationships:** This included relationships at home, such as with siblings and parents.
- **More Confidence:** One of the most important qualities to develop for children, students and young adults.
- **Better Sleep:** The importance of proper sleep in being understood more and more in today's hectic sleep deprived world.
- **Headache Relief:** Always a good thing.
- **Calmness:** Same as blood pressure above, it helped the students who learned meditation remain calm even during stressful times. This is important in all aspects of life I feel.
- **Sharper Brains:** I have often alluded to meditation helping the brain function well. This and other research that looks at brain imaging, etc, is now validating this point as well.

In this contexts researcher has done this research in her institution to find out usefulness and effects of mindfulness meditation of students.

Introduction-:

The term "mindfulness" has been used to refer to a psychological state of awareness, the practices that promote this awareness, a mode of processing information and a character trait. Define mindfulness as a moment-to-moment awareness of one's experience without judgment. In this sense, mindfulness is a state and not a trait. Mindfulness is the practice of paying attention to our present moment experience, whether it be a sight, a sound, a taste, a smell, a sensation, in the body, or mental activity. (the latter includes emotions and thoughts).

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Mindful interventions in primary and secondary schools could potentially promote both Social-Emotional Learning and application of mathematical methods. Mindful perspective-taking for students with different socio-cultural backgrounds may promote context-dependent social-emotional awareness. Mindful search for alternative solutions could also promote instructional width, increasing the likelihood that students will apply the different methods being taught. The process of seeking different perspectives celebrates diversity and integration, eventually resulting in improved life satisfaction. The classroom application of Mindfulness is a compelling and potentially paradigm-shifting area of future educational research.

In this contexts researcher has done this research in her institution to find out usefulness and effects of mindfulness meditation of students. This paper focuses on the **Effect of mindfulness Meditation on the B.Ed. students**

Need of research

Modern life is full of stressful situations, fatigue from long hours and little sleep, allergies, anxiety disorders and a long list of stress-related diseases. Adding mindfulness meditation to your life will improve the quality and possibly the quantity of your life. Improved health means you can participate in more physical activities and just feel better in the things you do daily.

Statement of the Problem

“A Survey of Effect of Mindfulness Meditation on the Students of G.S.B’s Smt. Surajba College of Education.”

Need of the Study

Modern life is full of stressful situations, fatigue from long hours and little sleep, allergies, anxiety disorders and a long list of stress-related diseases. Adding mindfulness meditation to your life will improve the quality and possibly the quantity of your life. Improved health means you can participate in more physical activities and just feel better in the things you do daily.

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Scope of the Study

The present study is confined to the mindful meditation B.Ed. students A sample of 100 students was taken to get the data.

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives are framed for the present study by the researcher.

1. To find out the effect of mindful meditation of B.Ed. students.
2. To find out different reasons of mindful meditations effect.
3. To find out solution and remedies for complete mindful meditations effect.

Method of Research

The present study involves survey method. The investigator selected this method because it is only status study.

Sample of the Study

After a detailed study of all the sampling methods and considering the variables selected for the research work, the stratified sampling method was found suitable. Hundred B.Ed. students taken for the present study.

Tools of the Study

Among the research procedures, selection of suitable tools to the study is also an important one. For research Torontos Mindfulness scale tool used for the present study.

Analysis of Data

The data collected through the use of tools need to be sorted out, organized, edited, classified and tabulated for the convenience of further use before the analysis and interpretation of data to get generalization and to make conclusions.

Q.1 I experienced myself as separate from my changing thoughts and feelings.

- Survey shows following findings:-

Not at all	A little	moderately	Quite a bit	Very much
9.37%	25.94%	29.3%	35.93%	00.00

Student's survey shows they have experiences them self's as separate from their changing thoughts and feelings. 35% students said quite bit, 25.94% students said A little, 29.3% students said moderately. It shows that they cannot separate their changing thoughts and feelings at highest level.

Q.2 I was more concerned with being open to my experiences than controlling or changing them.

Not at all	A little	moderately	Quite a bit	Very much
9%	18.75%	33.48%	23.44%	15.63%

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This table shows opening their experiences than controlling or changing them. 9% students said Not at all, 18.75% students said A little, 33.48% students said moderately, 23.44% students said quite a bit, 15.63% students said Very much.

Q.3 I was curious about what I might learn about myself by taking notice of how I react to certain thoughts feelings or sensations.

Not at all	A little	moderately	Quite a bit	Very much
14.06%	17.18%	23.43%	25%	18.75%

This table shows students were curious about what I might learn about myself by taking notice of how I react to certain thoughts feelings or sensations. 14.06% students said Not at all, 17.18% students said A little, 23.43% students said moderately, 25.00% students said quite a bit, 18.75% students said Very much.

Q.4 I experienced my thoughts more as events in my mind than as a necessarily accurate reflection of the way things really are.

Not at all	A little	moderately	Quite a bit	Very much
7.81%	23.43%	23.43%	29.68%	17.19%

This table shows students have experienced their thoughts more as events in their mind than as a necessarily accurate reflection of the way things really are. 14.06% students said Not at all, 17.18% students said A little, 23.43% students said moderately, 29.68% students said quite a bit, 17.19% students said Very much

Q.5 I was curious to see what my mind was up to from moment to moment .

Not at all	A little	moderately	Quite a bit	Very much
9	18.75	33.48	23.44	15.63

This table shows students were curious to see what their mind was up to from moment to moment . 9% students said Not at all, 18.75% students said A little, 33.48% students said moderately, 23.44% students said quite a bit, 15.63% students said Very much.

Q.6 I was curious about each of the thoughts and feelings that I was having

Not at all	A little	moderately	Quite a bit	Very much
9	18.75	33.48	23.44	15.63

This table shows students was curious about each of the thoughts and feelings that they were having . 9% students said Not at all, 18 .75% students said A little, 33.48% students said moderately, 23.44%students said quite a bit, 15.63% students said Very much

Q.7 I was receive to observings unpleasant thoughts and feelings without interfering with them

Not at all	A little	moderately	Quite a bit	Very much
7.81%	15.62%	31.25%	20.31%	15.62%

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This table shows students have received to observings unpleasant thoughts and feelings without interfering with them. 7.81% students said Not at all, 15.62 % students said A little, 31.25 % students said moderately, 20.31 %students said quite a bit, 15.62 % students said Very much

Q.8 I was more invested in just watching my experiences as they arose , than in figuring out what they could mean.

This table shows students was more invested in just watching there experiences as they arose , than in figuring out what they could mean. 7.81% students said Not at all, 10 % students said A little, 15.62% students said moderately, 16.62 % students said quite a bit, 15.62 % students said Very much.

Q.9 I Approached Each Experience By Trying To Accept It, No Matter Whether It Was Pleasant Or Unpleasant.

Not at all	A little	moderately	Quite a bit	Very much
10.93%	18.75	31.25	23.43	15.62

This table shows students approached each experience by trying to accept it, no matter whether it was pleasant or unpleasant. 10.93% students said Not at all, 18.75 % students said A little, 33.48% students said moderately, 23.43 % students said quite a bit, 15.62 % students said Very much.

Q.10 I remained curious about the nature of each experience as it arose.

Not at all	A little	moderately	Quite a bit	Very much
9	18.75	33.48	23.44	15.63

This table shows students remained curious about the nature of each experience as it arose. 9.00 % students said Not at all, 18.75 % students said A little, 33.48% students said moderately, 23.44 % students said quite a bit, 15.63 % students said Very much.

Q.11 I was aware of my thoughts and feelings without over identifying with them

Not at all	A little	moderately	Quite a bit	Very much
4.68	15.62	31.25	21.88	15.62

This table shows students were aware of their thoughts and feelings without over identifying with them. 4.68 % students said Not at all, 15.62 % students said A little, 31.25% students said moderately, 21.88 % students said quite a bit, 15.62 % students said Very much.

Q.12 I was curious about what I might learn about myself by just taking notice of what may attention gets drawn to.

Not at all	A little	moderately	Quite a bit	Very much
10.94	15.62	31.25	28.12	14.06

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This table shows students was curious about what they might learn about themselves by just taking notice of what attention gets drawn to. 10.94 % students said Not at all, 15.62 % students said A little, 31.25% students said moderately, 28.12 % students said quite a bit, 14.06 % students said Very much.

Q.13 Have you done meditation for fullness anytime.

N	Not at all	A little	moderately	Quite a bit	Very much
9.37	18.75	46.87	12.5	12.5	

This table shows students has done meditation for mindfulness anytime. 09.37 % students said Not at all, 18.75 % students said A little, 48.87% students said moderately, 12.05 % students said quite a bit, 12.05 % students said Very much.

Discussions and Conclusions:-

- Researcher found benefits of mindfulness meditation among a young group who participated in mindfulness training. In this research meditation practice was directly related to self-reported positive affect and inversely related to self-reported negative effect.
- Researcher found that the meditation group had significantly better performance on all measures of attention and had higher self-reported mindfulness. Mindfulness meditation

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- practice and self-reported mindfulness were correlated directly with cognitive flexibility and intentional functioning
- Research also supports the notion that mindfulness meditation decreases emotional reactivity. Study found that students who practice mindfulness meditation appear to develop the skill of self-observation.
- Research found that a person's ability to be mindful can help predict relationship satisfaction — the ability to respond well to relationship stress and the skill in communicating one's emotions to a partner.
- Research found that Mindfulness has been shown to enhance self-insight, morality, intuition and fear modulation.
- Research found that students reported less anxiety and depressive symptoms.
- Better quality of life. Using qualitative and quantitative measures, nursing students reported better quality of life and a significant decrease in negative psychological symptoms.

Benefits of Mindfulness:-

Mindfulness is seen to have its roots in ancient Eastern, primarily Buddhist, traditions. However, there are enough references in Hindu scriptures that emphasize on meditation, silence and acceptance, which is what mindfulness, is about.

Mindfulness is the practice of purposely focusing your attention on the present moment—and accepting it without judgment. Mindfulness is now being examined scientifically and has been found to be a key element in happiness.

Ancient roots, modern applications - The cultivation of mindfulness has roots in Buddhism, but most religions include some type of prayer or meditation technique that helps shift your thoughts away from your usual pre-occupations toward an appreciation of the moment and a larger perspective on life.

Mindfulness improves well being

- Increasing your capacity for mindfulness supports many attitudes that contribute to a satisfied life.

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- Being mindful makes it easier to savor the pleasures in life as they occur, helps you become fully engaged in activities, and creates a greater capacity to deal with adverse events.
- By focusing on the here and now, many people who practice mindfulness find that they are less likely to get caught up in worries about the future or regrets over the past, are less preoccupied with concerns about success and self-esteem, and are better able to form deep connections with others.

Mindfulness improves physical health

If greater well-being isn't enough of an incentive, scientists have discovered the benefits of mindfulness techniques help improve physical health in a number of ways. Mindfulness can:

- Help relieve stress
- Treat heart disease
- Lower blood pressure
- Reduce chronic pain
- Improve sleep
- Improve gastrointestinal difficulties

Mindfulness improves mental health

In recent years, psychotherapists have turned to mindfulness meditation as an important element in the treatment of a number of problems, including:

- Depression
- Eating disorders
- Anxiety disorders
- Obsessive-compulsive disorder
- Stress Management
- Increased Flexibility
- Emotional Boost
- Improved Health

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Suggestions for Further Research

Studies may be taken up to identify the other factors affecting on mindfulness meditation.

Conclusion

Researchers put forward that mindfulness meditation promotes met cognitive awareness, decreases rumination via disengagement from preservative cognitive activities and enhances attention capacities through gains in working memory. These cognitive gains, in turn, contribute to effective emotion-regulation strategies.

More specifically, research on mindfulness has identified these benefits:

- Reduced rumination.
- Stress reduction.
- Boosts to working memory.
- Focus on the work
- Less emotional reactivity. .
- More cognitive flexibility.
- Relationship satisfaction.
- Enhance self-insight,
- Morality, intuition and fear modulation
- Increased immune functioning,
- Mindfulness meditation practice appears to increase information processing speed
- Mindfulness promotes empathy.
- Enhance self-compassion

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